

10TH EUROPEAN CONGRESS ON HEAD & NECK ONCOLOGY

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ABSTRACT BOOK

LOC

PCO

ORAL COMMUNICATIONS

- OC008** The development of a decision aid for operable oropharyngeal carcinoma, a mixed methods study
- OC015** Diagnostic test accuracy of sentinel lymph node biopsy in larynx & pharynx cancers: a meta-analysis
- OC016** Deep learning NTCP model for late dysphagia based on 3D dose, CT and segmentations
- OC022** IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN HEAD AND NECK CANCER DIAGNOSIS
- OC028** Effects of popliteal nerve blocks on postoperative pain after fibular free flap reconstruction
- OC033** Adherence to prophylactic swallowing exercises during head neck radiotherapy – the PRESTO-trial

- PO207** Adenoid cystic carcinomas of salivary glands treated with carbon ion radiotherapy at CNAO
- PO209** Is there an over-indication for elective tracheostomy in patients with oral cavity cancer?
- PO210** Chemoradiotherapy in Oropharyngeal Malignancies -Are we ready to De-escalate Radiotherapy protocols?
- PO212** Efficacy of relative intact parathormone levels in predicting hypocalcemia after total thyroidectomy
- PO214** Determining the efficacy of Nimotuzumab as a radiosensitizer in head and neck malignancies.
- PO215** Negative pressure wound therapy: salvage option for pharyngocutaneous and tracheoesophageal fistula.
- PO216** Impact of nutritional counseling for Head and Neck Cancer patients undergoing radiochemotherapy
- PO217** Paranasal sinus and nasal cavity carcinoma: experience of a tertiary hospital
- PO218** Chemoradiotherapy with curative intent in head and neck cancer – experience from a cancer center
- PO219** Internal mammary artery perforator (IMAP) flap for head and neck oncological defects reconstruction
- PO220** Reirradiation with particle therapy in recurrent sinonasal carcinoma: a single institution results
- PO221** Intratumoral necrosis in head and neck cancer following hadrontherapy: the role of dose, RBE and LET
- PO222** Laryngeal chondrosarcoma, the experience of an oncologic center
- PO223** Feasibility study of Infrahyoid flap in oral tongue reconstruction after compartmental glossectomy
- PO224** VEGF-A gene -460 C/T polymorphism – potential genetic marker for overall survival in OSCC patients
- PO227** A dynamic, cancer specific patient reported experience measure item-bank: a mixed method approach

- PO228** IMAP flap: a reliable option for neck reconstruction
- PO230** Transoral Ultrasonic Surgery (TOUSS): a safe and effective alternative for Head and Neck tumors.
- PO231** 3D printed immobilization devices for radiotherapy dedicated MRI of head and neck cancers
- PO232** Voice Outcome After Uncomplicated Thyroidectomy in Patients With Papillary Carcinoma
- PO233** Reconstruction of large skull base defects after tumor resection
- PO234** Pharyngocutaneous Fistula Following Total Laryngectomy
- PO238** Electrochemotherapy in Head and Neck Melanoma - Re-

glossectomy in a resource constrained settings and in patients unfit for free flap reconstruction.

PO-224 | VEGF-A gene -460 C/T polymorphism – potential genetic marker for overall survival in OSCC patients

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Purpose/Objective

The vascular endothelial growth factor A gene (VEGF-A) is located on 6p21.1 and its product induces proliferation and migration of vascular endothelial cells. The objective of this study was to evaluate vascular endothelial growth factor A (VEGF-A) gene polymorphism -460 C/T (rs833061) as potential genetic marker for overall survival in oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) patients.

Material/methods

In total, 61 samples of paraffin-embedded tissue taken during the surgery from patients diagnosed with OSCC, served for further molecular testing. All patients were older than 18 years and total follow up period was for 3 years. Adequate adjuvant therapy related to postoperative risk was applied. Data were collected on the overall survival of the patients. Genomic DNA was isolated using the QIAamp DNA FFPE Tissue Kit (Qiagen). Region including polymorphism of the VEGF-A gene at the position -460 C/T was amplified and PCR amplicons were sequenced. Sequence analysis was performed in BioEdit (Hall, 1999), and the genotypes were scored. All of the statistical analyses were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics. The Chi-square test of independence was used to determine if there is a significant relationship between two categorical variables.

Results

The VEGF-A -460 C/T genotype was successfully determined for all 57 patients. The mean age of patients was 65.4 ± 10.1 . The most frequent genotype was CT 24 (42.1%), followed by CC 20 (35.1%), while TT genotype was detected in 13 (22.8%) patients. There is statistically significant relationship between VEGF-A -460 C/T genotype and overall survival (chi-square=6.550, df=2 p=0.038). More than half of non-survived patients in 3 year follow up period had genotype CT, while most of survived patients after 3 year follow-up period had CC (47%). Only 14% of non-survived patients had genotype CC, while one third of them had TT genotype.

Conclusion

Homozygotes CC at VEGF-A -460C/T polymorphism (rs833061) showed longer overall survival. This SNP is located in the promoter region of VEGF-A gene and previous association studies including different cancer types yielded conflicting results. In our study we showed that this polymorphism might be potential new marker for overall survival in OSCC patients. In order to further evaluate it, it would be beneficial to conduct a survey in healthy control and to increase study population size.

PO-227 | A dynamic, cancer specific patient reported experience measure item-bank: a mixed method approach

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Objective

Since the introduction of value based healthcare there is an increased attention for the use of Patient Reported Experience Mea-